

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18979531](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18979531)

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Assessment of Rad-hardness in Microwave ICs for Navigational and Instrumental Uses in Space (ARMINIUS)</i>
Project TA identifier	TA13-412
General application	Space
Type of test	SEE
Group leader, Institute	<i>Roberto Materni, Saphyrion Sagl</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	
Date(s) of the experiment	11.09.2025
Facility	<i>Heavy Ion Facility (HIF) of the Centre de Ressources du Cyclotron, Université Catholique de Louvain (UCL)</i>
Amount of access granted	8h

Objectives of the experiments

The purpose of this test session is to assess single event effects hardness of the GNSS AD convert Saphyrion SY1019 chip up to a LET = 85 MeV · cm²/mg.

The choice of the ion species depends substantially on the LET and penetration into the silicon material required for the test. The SY1019 is meant to operate up to a LET of 85 MeV · cm²/mg and the beam flux should reach at least 17.5 μm of penetration. For this test, Xenon ¹²⁴Xe³⁵⁺ has been chosen with an energy of 1 GeV. At the silicon surface the LET results to be 63 MeV · cm²/mg at 0° and 89.5 MeV · cm²/mg at 45° tilt.

Experiment test report

The SY1019 ADC has been tested in this session. The device is designed and manufactured using the XFAB XH018A 180 nm CMOS process. Advance information datasheet can be downloaded on Saphyrion web site: "SY1019 3-bit AD-Converter/DDC ADVANCE INFORMATION, Literature Number: DSSY1019 April 19, 2024, Rev. 1.1"

The SY1019 test items (DUTs) used for this heavy ion irradiation test session are the following:

- **GDS layout cell name (SPH database):** SY1019V5 1.gds.
- **Part Number:** SY1019 [1].
- **Die Marking:** 2023-V5 SY1019
- **Die size:** 2790 μm X 1820 μm with scribe line
- **Test board (PCB):** TB1019.
- **Process:** XFAB XH018A 180 nm CMOS process.
- **DUTs tested:** 3x – DUT-TB1, DUT-TB2, DUT-TB6.

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According to ESCC25100 standard, which describes the SEE test methods and guidelines, the heavy ion accelerator shall be capable of delivering ions with a range of at least 40 μm in silicon with variable ion flux ranging from a few 10 ions/cm²/s to at least 10E+04 ions/cm²/s on the device under test. The total accumulated flux must reach at least a recommended fluence of 10E+06 ions/cm². The beam flux during the test was set to about 15E+03 ions/cm²/s, for a tilt of 45° this corresponds to an ion flux source of 10.5E+03 ions/cm²/s, which takes 950 s (16 min) to reach a total fluence of 10E+06 ions/cm². For this test, Xenon ¹³⁶Xe³⁵⁺ has been chosen with an energy of 1 GeV. At the silicon surface the LET results to be 63 MeV · cm²/mg at 0° and 89.5 MeV · cm²/mg at 45° tilt. In summary, the test configuration was set as follows:

- **Ions:** Xenon, ¹²⁴Xe³⁵⁺
- **Average Beam flux:** $\approx 15\text{E}+03$ ions/cm²/s at tilt = 0°, $\approx 10.5\text{E}+03$ ions/cm²/s at tilt = 45°
- **Total accumulated flux:** $>10\text{E}+06$ ions/cm² (approx. 16min)
- **Energy at DUT:** ≈ 1 GeV
- **Tilt: 45° (LET = 89.5 MeV · cm²/mg)**

The DUTs were tested at temperatures of 125°C and device maximum low and high supply voltages for SEU and SEL tests respectively. During the test all registers were logged and displayed on the tester application every second. The registers must maintain their initial value: an error is detected when a register value changes compared to its initial value. If an error occurs and the DUT is still operative the test will continue, if the DUT enters an inoperative state, it will be reset and the test will then continue without stopping the beam.

The measured currents and voltages are logged and aren't allowed to change more than 10% of the initial value. If a drift $>10\%$ is measured it will be considered an error. If a latch-up occurs it will be logged, then released by power cycling the affected DUT. If the DUT is still operative the test will then continue on the same DUT until a fluence of $\geq 10^7$ particles/cm² is accumulated.

The conditions for these tests are the following:

Nr	AVDD/LVDD	DVDD	Temper.	Test Conditions
1	1.6V	2.7V	125°C	Worst-case AVDD, LVDD and DVDD and temperature for SEU test.
2	2.0V	3.6V	125°C	Worst-case AVDD, LVDD and DVDD and temperature for SEL test.

During the irradiation period different data were logged. Several parameters have been selected as event indicators; these are shown in Table 5 and comprise both analog parameters and DUT register status. DVDD is the positive supply voltage of the pad-ring, LVDD is digital supply of the digital core part of the chip and AVDD is the positive supply voltage for the analog ADC converter part of the chip. VBG is an internal Band-gap voltage regulator.

Registers	Measured Value	Notes
ANALOG OUT1 VOLTAGE	VBG [mV]	
ANALOG OUT2 CURRENT	DVDD Current [μA]	
ANALOG OUT3 VOLTAGE	DVDD [mV]	
ANALOG OUT4 CURRENT	AVDD Current [μA]	
ANALOG OUT5 VOLTAGE	AVDD [mV]	
ANALOG OUT6 CURRENT	LVDD Current [μA]	
ANALOG OUT7 VOLTAGE	LVDD [mV]	

CTRL Register, Address = 0x00	136	
NCO LSB Register, Address = 0x01	0	
NCO MSB Register, Address = 0x02	0	
RSSI LSB , Address = 0x03	128	
RSSI MSB , Address = 0x04	140	
interface DIGITAL IN SP0	15	It is the decimal value of SY1019 In-phase (I) path 4-bits output

These parameters were selected because they are measurable sensitive parameters affected by irradiation. The band-gap voltage reference (V_{BG}) – which uses CMOS in a circuit with relatively high gain and is used to bias all circuits in the DUTs – is a rather sensitive precision circuit that is a good indicator of possible radiation induced degradation or damages. SEU will be detected as changes in the CTRL Register and NCO Register and the corresponding effects on current consumption.

The register holding the RSSI could be affected by SEUs, because the DSP function that computes this value is not protected against SEE events. However, any impact on the RSSI register would be transient, since the RSSI value is recalculated and updated into the register every 2¹⁵ clock cycles.

Results:

Heavy ions tests up to **LET = 89.5 MeV · cm²/mg** and a fluence of **10⁷ particles/cm²** were conducted on four samples of the SY1019 device to evaluate their sensitivity to single event effects. These tests gave the following results:

- The DUTs showed no failure, damage or significant drifts degradation due to heavy ions irradiation. The variations are due more to measurement tolerances, temperature and quantization effects rather than drifts in the DUTs.
- The SY1019 DUTs showed no latch-up (SEL) for any of the tested combination of supply voltage and temperature.
- The SY1019 DUTs showed some SEEs due to heavy ions irradiation during SEE condition. The SEEs are:
 - one single SEU in the RSSI registers is showed, in all 4 test boards, during the full radiation run sessions: the register holding the RSSI could be affected by SEUs, as expected, because the DSP function that computes this value is not protected against SEE events. Any impact on the RSSI register would be transient, since the RSSI value is recalculated and updated into the register every 2¹⁵ clock cycles.
 - one single SEU in the SY1019 4-bits output value in test board TB6: during the SEL test, a change was observed in the SY1019 4-bits output because the NCO (Numerically Controlled Oscillator) phase has changed. The NCO register that defines the phase increment (and therefore the output frequency) did not change state during the test — all other related registers were verified to be correct. This indicates that only the internal phase accumulator of the NCO was affected. This part of the circuit is protected using Triple Modular Redundancy (TMR). Given that the event was observed only once during more than 140 minutes of radiation testing in total, it is very likely that a double Single Event Upset (SEU) occurred within the same clock cycle in the TMR path. Such an occurrence is rare but physically possible, as two simultaneous bit upsets can temporarily defeat the TMR's voting logic and result in a transient error in the output.

This test session has demonstrated that the SY1019 device have low sensitivity to SEU and no sensitivity to SEL due to heavy ions irradiation up to a LET = 89.5 MeV · cm²/mg and confirms the effectiveness of the design methodologies and layout techniques used to counteract SEE.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
The successfully HI tests approve the final design of the device. Next step is the wafer production and the HI tests on the silicon dies taken from wafers, this will allow to apply for ESA ESCC9000 qualification for space flight parts components	X

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008126.